

EFFECTIVE WAYS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES THROUGH DIFFERENT RESOURCES

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Abstract:

In this article, we are going to study some efficient methods for acquiring a new language. If we learn hard, exactly, we will achieve all targets. There are several useful ways for learning foreign languages. These methods are vital to all learners.

Key words: best ways, mistakes, tips from expert, challenges, learning track, vocabulary.

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Learning a new language is challenging, frustrating, and sometimes just downright difficult. And figuring out the best way to learn a new language? That seems nearly impossible. Different science, theories, and learning styles are all over the place, and truthfully, some languages are easier to learn than others. Despite the difficulties, multi-language acquisition is rapidly growing in popularity around the world and bilinguality is becoming more of a highly-desired resume addition .

There are the best ways of learning another language:

1. Make New Friends

Friendship is one of the best ways to learn a foreign language, and the easiest way to get comfortable with the slang, intonation, and mannerisms. You can casually chat with your friends in local cafés, bars, and restaurants and slowly build a foundation on the language you want to learn. The great part about making friends who already speak the language (or are learning right along with you) is that you will be able to practice freely without feeling self-conscious or on the spot!

2. Watch a Movie

For the people who want to take advantage of one of the best ways to learn a language from the comfort of their own home, put on a foreign movie in another language — without subtitles if you can! Not only is this one of the best ways to learn a foreign language, but you will also get a greater sense of that language's culture as well! If you do not know enough of the language to turn the subtitles off, keep a list of new vocabulary words you hear and what you think they mean.

3. Seek Out Online Resources

You can connect with other language learners via online chat groups, watch YouTube videos, and read articles. The internet is ready to help you reach your foreign language learning goals!

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4. Teach Yourself

The key to this one is small steps of dedicated research – and while obvious, remains one of the best ways to learn a new language. Take a little bit of time every day to write out a sentence you would like to know how to say in your target language. Look up each word section and try to construct the sentence yourself. If you have a language partner, have them double check your sentences when you meet up. This is a great trick to keep yourself in check. Making small goals to attain every day will keep you moving onward and upward on the language learning track!

5. Go Abroad!

One of the best ways to learn a foreign language is to visit a country that speaks your target language and live with a host family that does not speak your native language. You will be absolutely amazed at how much information you can communicate and how quickly you pick up a language when you do not have any other option. This full-on immersion style training will have you speaking fluently in months [2, 13].

And one of the best ways to learn a new language (or learn anything, really) is to make a lot of mistakes. Do not roll your eyes just yet! As frustrating as mistakes can be, they actually provide us with great opportunities to learn – once they are corrected, of course. Corrective feedback is a form of input your brain can use to help you avoid making the mistake a second time. But even if you do make the same mistake again, do not worry! Making mistakes can be evidence of learning. You heard that right! In the process of learning a language, there is a stage (even when children learn their first languages) where we make systematic, patterned errors. Thinking in the language you are learning is so useful a way. As strange as it may initially seem, thinking in the language you are learning is an effective way to build your fluency. A common pitfall for language learners is to think of what they want to say (or write) in their first language, and then translate it into their second language. But language learning involves a lot more than translation, and there are many concepts and phrases that can not be translated. For example, imagine you would like to use the idiom, “It is raining cats and dogs!” in Spanish. The literal translation (*está lloviendo gatos y perros*) does not make sense in Spanish. The equivalent Spanish phrase is *llueve a cántaros*, which translates literally to “it is raining (or it rains) pitchers!” [1, 10].

Moreover there are the most effective way to learn a new language – spaced repetition too. This technique is a long-standing technique that has been used by countless people over the years as a way of improving the speed at which they learn a new language. Spaced repetition helps you memorize new vocabulary. To practice this technique, you need to review the words and phrases you have learned in specific intervals. In the beginning, these intervals should be on the short side. You might need to review new words or phrases a couple of times or more per session at first, then look at them the next day too. Once a phrase is stuck, you can start leaving days or weeks between revising it. This was always an argument we used as a teacher when discussing the timetabling of language lessons in high school. One year, the exam classes had all three of their week’s language lessons in one day as a triple lesson. It made spaced repetition impossible unless you relied on the students to do it in their own time! [3, 12].

There are tips from experts to learn a language quickly. For instance:

- Take risks and speak the language whenever you can.
- Read children's books and comic books in the foreign language.
- Consume foreign language media.
- Immerse yourself in the local culture.
- Make use of free foreign language podcasts and apps.
- Do not practice in isolation; get feedback from native speakers.
- Do not worry about making mistakes [4, 3].

Each learner's particular goals and style of learning will determine the most effective method for them. Learners of new languages may face a few challenges in the upcoming year, but there can also be fulfilling rewards. Gaining a respect for many cultures and people, as well as enhancing your creativity and other brain processes, are all benefits of learning a new language.

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